

Boosting behavioral change and citizens' engagement in cities through technology: the DivAirCity project approach

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Abstract—Cities are complex vivid structures that are affected by multiple factors, such as economic activity, climate change, and social inclusion which affect people living in them. Air pollution and climate resilience are key factors affecting people's health and well-being in urban areas. Their impact is more pronounced in the most deprived and vulnerable parts of the population, living in poorer urban areas. DivAirCity is a H2020 project that aims to address these challenges by embracing human diversity to shape innovative urban services and models and Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), fostering culturally driven green cities. The project also introduces two key digital tools to facilitate its objectives: a blockchain-based application (dApp) and a federated data system, both designed to support participatory decision-making, behavioral change and citizens' engagement through the collection and visualization of air quality data, tokenization and rewarding. In addition to promoting urban sustainability, these tools and their outcome can provide valuable resources for students of engineering, developers, and social engagement stakeholders.

Keywords—behavioural change, social diversity, digital tools, scientific science, air quality, carbon neutral cities, mobile application

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban environments are shaped by economic activities, climate change, pollution, and social factors, with cities playing a key role in the European Green Deal for 2030. However, not all citizens have equal influence in urban planning. Poor air quality in European cities causes over 500,000 deaths annually, disproportionately affecting marginalized communities. Disadvantaged groups, including ethnic minorities and lower-income populations, live in areas with high pollution levels due to dense housing, limited green spaces, and heavy traffic. Although wealthier neighborhoods enjoy better air quality, they have higher per capita carbon footprints. Ethnic disparities in pollution exposure are evident in Spain and Sweden, where non-European immigrants face worse conditions [1] – [5].

The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated social inequalities, with polluted areas experiencing higher infection and death rates [7] – [9]. Research links long-term nitrogen dioxide exposure to respiratory diseases, disproportionately affecting

ethnic minorities [10]. Despite increasing evidence of these inequalities, marginalized voices remain excluded from policymaking, reinforcing systemic biases. The European Commission (EC) highlights challenges such as economic instability, globalization, and climate change in fostering inclusive urban diversity [6].

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) offer a promising approach to addressing pollution and promoting sustainability by cooling urban areas, removing pollutants, and enhancing mental well-being [11], [5]. However, for NBS to be truly equitable, they must involve participatory decision-making rather than top-down expert-driven solutions. While co-design approaches aim to ensure social inclusion, evidence of their success remains limited, with some projects inadvertently reinforcing inequalities. Additionally, behavioral change can act as a driver towards climate neutrality, decarbonizations and improvement of health and well-being [12], [13].

Another field involving citizens' engagement is Citizen Science (CS). CS refers to the growing trend of engagement of individuals, who belong to the public, without necessarily having scientific expertise, and involve them in collecting, categorizing, transcribing, or analyzing scientific data [14]. CS covers wide scientific fields, such as biodiversity, environment, health, social sciences and digital governance [15, 16]. The purpose of CS is twofold. First, it supports scientific research by engaging the public in generating and analyzing large, diverse datasets. Second, it enhances public interest and participation in science, thus serving an educational role. A review of the scientific and educational outcomes of CS is available in [17].

Digital innovative tools have transformed co-design and CS by enabling large-scale, online data collection and tracking and increased project visibility [15]. These tools are easily available, typically released as applications in commercial mobile devices, thus significantly boosting citizens' engagement. Additionally, advancements in statistical tools and computing have simplified data collection and analysis, making them accessible for individuals with diverse culture and educational levels [15]. Many of them include certain incentives and gamification elements to increase their appeal and motivate participation.

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Participatory decision-making ensures equity and inclusion in urban sustainability is the basis for the core activities of DivAirCity, a H2020 funded project [18]. DivAirCity project aims to value diversity and social inclusion to achieve innovative, creative, culture-driven, green and carbon neutral urban society.

In the framework of DivAirCity digital tools have been developed as an enabler to citizens' behavioral change towards climate neutrality. Additionally, these tools facilitate the collection of critical air quality metrics, constituting a practical citizen science use case. In this respect these digital tools can also be utilized for wider educational purposes.

The rest of the paper is structured as: Section II is dedicated to a brief description of the DivAirCity project, Section III details the digital tools developed within the scope of the project as means of behavioral change and citizen science, Section IV discusses the educational value of the digital tools and Section V concludes the paper.

II. THE DIVAIRCITY PROJECT

DivAirCity is a H2020 funded project designed to address urban air pollution, climate change, and social inequality through NBS. It emphasizes the importance of inclusivity and social justice, building on EU insights. The core principle of DivAirCity is that NBS must be intentionally designed to address underlying social inequalities and tensions, focusing on empowering diversity groups in tackling air pollution and climate issues [19].

DivAirCity supports five pilot cities—Aarhus (DK), Bucharest (RO), Castellon (ES), Orvieto (IT), and Potsdam (DE) — along with at least 20 follower ones worldwide. The project involves diverse communities in addressing environmental challenges and adopts a bottom-up, participatory governance model that embraces multicultural communities and strives for an innovative, healthy, culturally vibrant, and sustainable urban society.

It focuses on six core dimensions of diversity, identified as "protected categories" under the United Nations's (UN) human rights framework: gender, age, ethnicity/race, sexual orientation, economic/social status, and physical/mental disabilities, with intersectionality being a key consideration. The project aims to shift urban decision-making from top-down processes to inclusive, horizontal dialogues, where these diverse groups play an active role in shaping NBS, not just in participatory activities, and to empower people from the 6+1 protected categories, ensuring their voices are heard and achieving both numerical and qualitative equality.

To tackle air pollution and carbon challenges in five European cities, DivAirCity will implement a range of concrete actions, including:

1. Inclusive participatory activities that prioritize engagement from the 6+1 protected categories
2. Equal representation of data to ensure diverse perspectives are acknowledged
3. Tailored frameworks and metrics to account for differing experiences
4. Co-designed urban interventions with the ambition of making them permanent
5. Development of services and solutions tailored to various community groups, particularly the protected categories.
6. New business models and smart city climate contracts that incorporate diversity-focused reward systems

7. Extensive media campaigns to raise awareness
8. Twinning initiatives to reinforce European values of diversity and collaborate with key networks

The project is part of the broader challenge of creating urban environments that are safe, healthy, and inclusive for all, rendering essential the development of new approaches to mitigate air pollution and to decarbonize. The challenge lays in considering the effects of rapid urban population growth and increasing pollution on marginalized communities.

DivAirCity aims to address the interconnected challenges of environmental (climate change and air pollution), societal (social inclusion vs. discrimination), and health (public health and well-being). Activities are based on testing and implementing new NBS strategies as the leading approach, and on employing cutting-edge technology in new digital tools to tackle the intersection of the environment, people, and health.

Fig. 1. DivAirCity: The power of Diversity & Inclusion for Climate Neutral Cities.

III. THE DIVAIRCITY DIGITAL TOOLS

Citizen engagement in the DivAirCity project is encouraged through the developed digital tools, (1) a cross-platform application for mobile devices based on Blockchain (BC) technology. The application is hybrid, operating as a distributed BC application (dApp) and at the same time as a conventional cloud-based application. (2) a federated data system, to operate as a bridge and reference point both to citizens but also all interested stakeholders. Both these tools are key features of the innovative part of the project.

A. The DivAirCity Blockchain application

The BC application supports the implementation of innovative Business Models (BMs) in Smart Cities contracts. BC technology enables transactions in a fully secured and tamperproof environment, protecting fully the privacy of the users. It provides also the users a trustful and easy to use interface, which is fully available, operational and efficient. and promotes financial independence for cities. It also facilitates direct interaction between cities and citizens, allowing more participatory city governance. The heart of the BC system is Smart Contracts, which are the 'rules of engagement'. These are computer programs stored in the BC which govern all transactions. They include all details, constraints and also the rewarding conditions.

Citizens can use BC easily by means of a mobile application, which functions in a distributed manner by invoking BC smart contracts through the system's BC nodes.

The citizens, especially those from diverse groups, using the distributed BC application are enabled to actively contribute to decarbonization efforts by promoting: (1) live carbon footprint tracking, (2) rewarding of emission reduction through environmentally friendly modes of transportation, and (3) rewarding for visiting designated urban green spaces and following green routes, which typically correspond to the project's implemented NBS.

The dApp creates an inclusive, transparent marketplace. Citizens are rewarded for using the different functionalities

of the dApp for decarbonization and air quality improvement. These rewards motivate citizens' engagement in the foreseen activities, boosting the expected results by the local urban interventions and allowing all citizens to participate in climate action and benefiting from their contributions. Specifically, the dApp provides incentives for eco-friendly behavior and citizen engagement, by rewarding with blockchain tokens, called DivAirCity tokens. These are virtual blockchain tokens that can be exchanged for actual goods and services, in a reward-based, inclusive marketplace. Citizens can also pledge their tokens in a donation campaign, such as tree planting. Finally, the exchange of tokens between different participating citizens is also available.

The application follows a wide range of requirements and specifications derived through DivAirCity actions and citizen co-creation initiatives to enhance citizen engagement in a privacy-compliant, secure, and diverse manner, especially focused on the 6+1 diversity groups. To this end, the dApp is compatible with multiple operating systems, specifically Android [20], iOS [21], and web-browsers [22]. It is designed with an easy-to-use UI/UX (User Interface/User Experience, incorporating guidelines of the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) [23] and modern design principles. It is released in the project's pilot cities local languages (Danish, Romanian, Spanish, Italian, German) and is compliant with national and European Union privacy requirements such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [24].

B. The DivAirCity Federated Data System

A federated data system (FDS) has been developed, which incorporates and visualizes data collected within the scope of the DivAirCity project, such as impact of the different project interventions, air-quality data by the project-installed air quality sensors or various statistical and air-quality data from the BC application. Further, existing external sources, such as data from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (AMS) [25], have been also integrated.

The data system, available through a web-browser, serves as a central hub for citizen science and behavioral change. It provides useful information to the citizens, regarding air quality at specific urban areas, ways to avoid polluted routes, and empowers them to contribute to the collected air-quality data through the DivAirCity dApp. Information is readily available by access to hourly air-quality data of the five pilot cities using current data or historical ones. Comparison with data by external sources, like Copernicus AMS gives useful information on the divergence of air quality indices in a specific area compared to the average ones.

From a behavioral change perspective, it motivates citizens to alter their daily routine to reduce air pollution, as the close-to-real time data availability enables informed choices such as, reducing car use, utilizing sustainable behavior, or initiating policy changes. Additionally, authorities can use the data to design targeted awareness campaigns and incentives that further encourage positive environmental actions. [Both the FDS and the BC application are on beta release, thus subject to changes following feedback provided by the users to make them more efficient and user friendly.](#)

C. Citizen Science and Behavioral Change

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 demonstrate an example of how the DivAirCity dApp is utilized to promote behavioral change.

Fig. 2a depicts the Summary screen of a citizen account, that is, the first page a user sees upon logging into the application. This screen displays their token balance, the daily traveled distance, and a counter showing the tokens earned on the current day. Fig. 2b showcases a Live Tracking session in progress, where the user's position is recorded via their mobile device's Global Positioning System (GPS). In the same figure, the user has also connected a compatible mobile air-quality sensor, to collect local air-quality data in a temporospatial manner. Specifically, during their Live Tracking session, the sensor records atmospheric particulate matter (PM), specifically, PM 1, PM 2.5 and PM 10, across their travelling routes. This data will then be uploaded to the federated data system, enabling the educational and scientific goals of citizen science. Fig. 3a shows the completion of the Live Tracking process, where a recap of the traveled distance is displayed along with a prompt to select the mode of transport used. If the citizens use environmentally friendly modes of transport, they will be rewarded with additional BC tokens, thus actively encouraging behavioral change. Anti-cheating measures prevent users from falsely selecting a mode of transport by cross-checking the recorded speed. Fig. 3b displays the updated Summary page after the conclusion of Live Tracking, where the daily earned token counter and daily traveled distance are updated.

In this example, the user earned 3.17 tokens for traveling 584 m in total. This reward is calculated based on several contributing factors: the citizen selected the On-Foot travel mode, which is set to reward 2 tokens/km; followed a designated green route rewarding 1.5 tokens; and submitted air quality data via their mobile sensor, earning an additional 0.5 tokens. Altogether, this results in a reward of $2 \cdot 0.584 + 1.5 + 0.5 = 3.17$ tokens as seen in the meter of Fig. 3b. Tokens earned during the day are added to the user's token balance at midnight (00:00 CET) and can subsequently be used in the BC marketplace or transferred to other citizens.

Fig. 2. Indicative screens of the DivAirCity dApp: (a) Summary screen prior to using the Live Tracking feature, (b) Live Tracking feature

Fig. 3. Indicative screens of the DivAirCity dApp: (a) Concluding Live Tracking and (b) Summary screen updated after concluding Live Tracking

IV. USAGE STATISTICS AND IMPACT METRICS

While the DivAirCity project does not mandate specific key performance indicators (KPIs) for the usage of the dApp, various impact metrics and usage statistics are derived from BC transactions and are publicly available through the FDS. These metrics are continuously reported, providing third stakeholders with insights such as the total number of tokens earned and donated, the total distance traveled per mode of transport over a given time and others. Between December 2024 and April 2025, i.e. the time following the beta release of the application for public use, 127 users-testers were using the application across the five pilot cities. During this period, over 400 km of travel was recorded in the Live Tracking sessions, along with 98 visits to designated Areas of Interest. Finally, five mobile sensors were used to collect air quality data during the live tracking. Even though the application is still in testing mode, the data shows that its main aspects were embraced by the citizens during the short period of its availability. Nevertheless, conclusive insights into the application's full impact on behavioral change will be available upon completion of the testing phase and the full release of the digital tools.

V. APPLICATIONS FOR EDUCATION IN ELECTRICAL AND INFORMATION ENGINEERING

Beyond promoting sustainability, the DivAirCity digital tools offer robust pedagogical value in courses such as BC technology, mobile application development, environmental data science, and social innovation. The interactive nature of the tool supports experiential learning and problem-based education, allowing students to engage directly with real-world challenges, such as pollution tracking, behavioral modeling, and citizen-driven data collection.

For example, a university-level course on mobile development or environmental engineering, could engage students in designing a dashboard that visualizes air quality data in real time using the DivAirCity dApp. Using air quality data collected via mobile sensors during dApp Live Tracking, location data and modes of transport, the users can develop interactive dashboards showing pollution exposure by transport type, summary reports that calculate emissions saved and comparative charts showing local vs. average city air quality using Copernicus data.

Furthermore, working with applications like the one in DivAirCity, engineering students gain an insight in the Blockchain architecture & smart contracts, potential developers in the UI/UX design and in secure mobile apps, environmental science students in Air quality monitoring and analysis and social science students in incentive design, civic participation and token-based reward systems. Therefore, this project not only deals with practical coding and data analysis but also introduces students to real-world sustainability challenges and public engagement mechanisms.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the DivAirCity H2020 project, focusing on the digital tools developed as means of citizen science and behavioral change. The main scope of the project is to tackle urban pollution, climate change, and social inequalities by using Nature-Based Solutions and smart digital tools. Two innovative tools have been developed: a blockchain-based distributed application and a federated data system. These tools facilitate behavioral change and sustainability by enabling citizens' engagement through the collection and visualization of air quality data, tokenization and rewarding. Apart from offering a practical solution for the mitigation of urban air-quality pollution, these technologies constitute a valuable resource for training courses on blockchain technology, mobile development, and social engagement, targeting electrical engineering students, developers, and social engagement practitioners.

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